

Estimating the Carbon Footprint of Bio-Based Materials in Asphalt Mixtures

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Supporting Information

Table 1. Life cycle inventory.

Stage	Unit process	Data source (inventory for the upstream processes)	
		Ukraine	Brazil
A1	Asphalt binder	Ecoinvent 3.11: pitch production, petroleum refinery operation Cut-off, U - Europe without Switzerland	Ecoinvent 3.11: pitch production, petroleum refinery operation Cut-off, U - BR
	Lignin	Donchenko, N. (2018)	-
	Polymer modifier	Donchenko, N. (2018)	-
	Derivative from tall oil	-	Ecoinvent 3.11: market for tall oil, crude Cut-off, U – GLO
A2	Lime	-	Ecoinvent 3.11: market for hydrated lime, packed Cut-off, U - RoW
	Agg.	Ecoinvent 3.11: gravel production, crushed Cut-off, U – RoW	Ecoinvent 3.11: gravel production, crushed Cut-off, U - BR
	Agg. and additive transport	Ecoinvent 3.11: transport, freight, lorry, 16-32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 3 Cut-off, U – RER	Ecoinvent 3.11: transport, freight, lorry, 16-32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 3 Cut-off, U - BR
	Neat binder transport	Ecoinvent 3.11: transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 3 Cut-off, U – RER	Ecoinvent 3.11: transport, freight, lorry, >32 metric ton, diesel, EURO 3 Cut-off, U - BR
A3	Materials' heating and asphalt binder storage	Ecoinvent 3.11: market for Heat, central or small-scale, natural gas Cut-off, U - Europe without Switzerland	Ecoinvent 3.11: market for Heat, central or small-scale, natural gas Cut-off, U - RoW Ecoinvent 3.11: heat production, heavy fuel oil, at industrial furnace 1MW Cut-off, U - RoW
	Plant operation	Ecoinvent 3.11: electricity, medium voltage market for Cut-off, U - UA	Ecoinvent 3.11: electricity, medium voltage market for Cut-off, U - BR-South-eastern/Mid-western grid}

*Agg: aggregate

References

1. Donchenko, N. (2018) Modification of Bitumens with Polymer and Natural Additives to Increase the Durability of Asphalt Concrete Pavements. Lviv University.